

INFLUENCE OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS ON TEACHERS' CAREER DEVELOPMENT AT PUBLIC SCHOOLS OF KARACHI SINDH, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This paper contains the discussion and finding about the teachers training and career development of government school in district South of Karachi. There have been efforts by the Department of Education and Literacy to invigorate the Teacher Training establishments for a long time now. In 2006, the education department decided to revive 42 teachers training institutes with the help of Canadian Debt Swap Assistance (Dawn, Aug 2006). This was planned after an assessment that the teachers hardly understood the material they taught and due to lack of pre service and in service training they could not manage class effectively, it was decided that the funds would be utilized to renovate the buildings of such institutions. According to the plan 510 faculty member of elementary education colleges were trained, 90 head teachers and 2700 Primary teachers and 690 Master Trainers were also trained. Vehicles were also provided and it was announce that all such training institutes will be converted into Professional Development Centers for the continuous training and career development of the teachers. However, the huge impact this initiative was supposed to make could not be seen on the ground and the results were not seen. This study is inspired by the efforts made for teacher training all over the country to see what impact those efforts have on ground and whether or not our schools have in-service trainings for teachers.

KEYWORDS: Career Development, Invigorate, Master Trainers, Professional Development Programs

INTRODUCTION

There have been efforts by the Department of Education and Literacy to invigorate the Teacher Training establishments for a long time now. In 2006, the education department decided to revive 42 teachers training institutes with the help of Canadian Debt Swap Assistance (Dawn, Aug 2006). This was planned after an assessment that the teachers hardly understood the material they taught and due to lack of pre service and in service training they could not manage class effectively, it was decided that the funds would be utilized to renovate the buildings of such institutions. According to the plan 510 faculty member of elementary education colleges were trained, 90 head teachers and 2700 Primary teachers and 690 Master Trainers were also trained. Vehicles were also provided and it was announce that all such training institutes will be converted into Professional Development Centers for the continuous training and career development of the teachers.(Dawn, Aug 2006). However, the huge impact this initiative was supposed to make could not be seen on the ground and the results were not seen. This study is inspired by the efforts made for teacher training all over the country to see what impact those efforts have on ground and whether or not our schools have in-service trainings for teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

No system of education is on top of the extent of its lecturers. Lecturers play a vital role within the system of education. It is vital that these lecturers are equipped with correct information, skills and attitudes in winding up the goals of education and fulfilling their obligations. Teachers coaching have bound levels that correspond with the final education ability of the lecturers. There are 3 levels of lecturer's coaching. Teachers for the first faculties' are trained, and should have passed middle school examination. They are provided one year coaching. When completion of this coaching they're awarded a certificate referred to as Primary Teacher's certificate (PTC). People who possess FA/F.Sc. certificate are given one year coaching and awarded a certificate referred to as Certificate in Education (CT). PTC and CT coaching is provided by the govt. schools of educational activity (GCEE). There are separate elementary schools of Education for ladies and boys World Health Organization are established the least bit the district headquarters at intervals the country. Those who possess BA/.Sc degrees are provided one year coaching referred to as "Bachelor of Education" (B.Ed) at the govt. schools of Education. These schools are at some elite places in every province of the country. people who any

wish to focus on the topic of education bear one year course referred to as Master in Education (M.Ed). This course is conducted by the colleges of Education and within the Institutes of Education within the Universities. Lecturers additionally do M.Phil and PH.D in Education from the schools. People who possess M.Ed or M.Phil teach within the schools of Education. At the University level PH.D scales are utilized to coach lecturers.

Allama Iqbal Open University has started teacher coaching courses through its distance education system for those students World Health Organization cannot afford to attend formal regular courses within the teacher coaching establishments. National Education policy (1998-2011) provides for modernizing the courses in lecturers coaching. Consequently, the length and amount of coaching the least bit levels of coaching is being increased, together with higher salaries for the lecturers. There are few issues within the teacher-training programme that embody non-availability of qualified teaching school for the colleges of Education, quality coaching programmes, money issues of the coaching establishments, lack of quality material for coaching and lack of effective system of management and superintendence. However the foremost significant issue is that the lecturers don't use those teaching skills and ways within their categories that were tutored to them in the coaching establishments.

National Education Policy (1998-2010) Teachers' coaching forms a vital part of the policy targets enclosed within the National Education Policy (1998-2010). The most objectives outlined within the National Education Policy in respect to teacher education embody the following, to extend the effectiveness of the system by institutionalizing in-service coaching of lecturers, teacher trainers and academic directors. To upgrade the standard of pre-service teacher coaching programmes, by introducing parallel programmes of longer length at post-secondary and post-degree levels. To form the teaching profession enticing to the young gifted graduates by institutionalizing a package of incentives. To develop a viable framework for policy, coming up with the development of teacher coaching programmes, each in-service and pre-service. The Policy stresses some key policy provisions for the coaching of teachers: each formal and non-formal suggests that shall be used, to supply increased opportunities of in-service coaching, to the lecturers ideally a minimum of once in 5 years. The information and therefore the ways of instruction in teachers' coaching establishments ought to be reviewed and revised, for delivery them the with the necessity of electronic equipment trends during this field; Special incentives shall be provided to draw in and retain gifted students within the teaching profession; A special package of incentives shall be provided to rural females to affix the teaching profession. A brand new stream of technical and (vocational coaching, vocational education, education) shall be introduced within the pre-service teachers' training establishments, initio at post-degree level, a brand new cadre of teacher educators shall be created.

Education Sector Reforms (2001-2005) and therefore the National arrange of Action (NPA). A lot of recently, the govt. has designed on the National Education Policy by developing a comprehensive package of academic reforms with medium term targets - the Education Sector Reforms (ESR) Action arrange for 2001-2005. The main thrust of ESR includes, besides enactment and social control of required Primary Education Ordinance and therefore the rehabilitation and upgrading of physical facilities in existing primary faculties, the development within the quality of education through Teacher Education and coaching. The provinces launched a significant teacher coaching initiative through their own and federal budgets since 2001. Over 175,000 teachers/lead trainers are trained at primary, middle and secondary levels. The ESR additionally is a foundation of the National arrange of Action (NPA) for Education for All developed as a semi permanent framework (2001-15) to attain EFA goals.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A Good Education is the right of every child and the focal point in the process of the successful teaching is the Teacher who makes a difference. A competent, passionate and alive teacher could make the walls, furniture, books and resources alive, else the best furniture and books remain dead. A trained and professionally groomed teacher could conduct a holistic development of a child by helping him develop physically, mentally, emotionally, ethically and aesthetically and that competent and skilled student is employable to lead a dignified life. However, in Pakistan, the 80% of student population who go to the Government schools, do not get a sound and comprehensive education and cannot compete the students graduating from private schools as they do not get the relevant competencies because of the untrained teachers. This study aims to explore whether or not the teachers of public schools have the opportunities for training and for the continuous professional development to impact these schools and to guarantee the progress of a child, it also seeks to find out what opportunities of training and career development could be provided to enhance their performance.

“Are there training and career development opportunities available for the teachers of government schools in Karachi district south to create an impact in their teaching”.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study aims to see are there any opportunities of training and career development available for the teachers of the government schools of district south. Trainings and Continuous Professional Development are keys to

success for any career and especially a field like education where a teacher is supposed to play his part in the holistic development of a student, it becomes essential that his or her administrative, academic and pedagogical skills are brushed from time to time to ensure good teaching. Education is about imparting Knowledge, Attitudes and Skills to complete the cycle of comprehensive circle of education and a teacher is supposed to know essential facts about every aspect of education. Thus continuous and effective trainings are needed to sensitize her. The researcher also wants to explore that how the teacher trainings, if any imparted, has affected the career development of the teachers because career development has become important in every career and no profession could remain effective unless a constant nurturing of the profession is done through proper trainings in the light of recent researches.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Do the Government Schools have any opportunities for teachers for Training and Career Development?
2. What in-service training programs and opportunities for career development of teachers in the Government schools are provided?
3. What is relation of Teacher Training and the Career Development, how career development could take place by promoting teacher trainings?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A mix design of Qualitative and Quantitative research will be applied to find out certain statistics as well as values and ethos related to training and career development of teachers in the government schools. Different research instruments will be used to collect the data like Questionnaires and Interviews of teachers and the school managers. The questions which could imply quantitative results are shown in tables and graphs and some of the open ended questions, which imply qualitative probing are covered in descriptive and inferential data.

POPULATION

Population is well defined collection of individuals who are selected for a particular research. The populations of the study are the selected teachers and the school managers. This sample population will help us collect the required data.

SAMPLING

For the teachers' interview, the stratified sampling will be used as the school system is stratified into Early Childhood Section, Primary and the Secondary Section. However, to collect data from the school managers multi stage sampling will be used by merging the simple random sampling, stratified sampling, Cluster sampling & systematic sampling.

SAMPLE

In research, sample is a group of people, items or institutions who are selected from a larger population to verify a hypothesis. Usually sample is a representative of a given population so that by sampling we may come to conclusions which could be generalize for the given population. Sampling is done from a research population having the same characteristics to ensure the accurate generalization. The research is conducted in four Government Girls Secondary Schools of District South i.e. SMB Fatima Jinnah Government Girls Secondary School, Mir Ayub Government Girls Secondary School, Fazalur Rahman Governemnt Girls Secondary School and New Ranchoreline Government Girls Secondary School. The sample size is 25 teachers from each school, total 100 teachers and five head teachers and school managers from each school, total 20. Teachers will be given the questionnaire while the school managers will be interviewed.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Research instruments are usually the devices through which the progress of a certain process is tested and measured. The research instruments for the current study are interviews and questionnaires; a thorough thought has been given to make the instrument valid and reliable.

VALIDITY & RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

Validity refers to an instrument whether it measures what it intended to measure and for that it is extremely important that the instrument is relevant and measures the desired tests. Validity is estimated in terms of content, construct, concurrence etc. The content, the construct, predictive nature and occurrence all have to be formed very carefully to suit the needs of a relevant test. The researcher therefore, reviewed the existing instruments and way of instrumentation before forming her questions for questionnaire and the interview trying to cover all the important aspects of the validity.

Reliability of a test proves that it would give the same result when used again, it is difficult for a researcher to claim for the generalization and his research being replicable without having independent observers and consistent research tools. In this study the researcher has taken care of the fact and has tried to make the research instrument as reliable as possible. Like no instrument in any research could be 100% valid or reliable, it cannot be claimed for the given study either. However, an effort has been made to make the research valid and reliable by using the most popular instruments which have been popularly used in similar kinds of researches. The accuracy and the connection between the questions were also scrutinized to assure the validity of the questions.

Since the setting to the government schools is more or less same in the targeted area, the research conclusions could be generalized.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND PROCEDURE

In the given study, a mixed method of both quantitative and qualitative research is used. The effect of the trained teachers is seen in numbers also and its impact on academic excellence and holistic development of the students is also discussed. The frequency of the training opportunities and its impact on teachers’ development will also be represented. Some inquiry for reaching on certain conclusion will also be the part of the analysis and some facts will be depicted by certain tables also.

DATA COLLECTION

Data Collection is a procedure through which relevant data is collected on targeted variables in a systematic way which could be measured and analyzed. In this study the data was collected by visiting the targeted four schools where the researcher has to take the permission of the Head Mistress of the school to be able to talk to the teachers and the school managers to talk about their experience, fears and feelings verbally besides answering the questionnaire.

DATA ANALYSIS

Q1. Do the Government Schools have any opportunities for teachers for Training and Career Development?

To the question as to teachers should get an opportunity to attend in-service or official training program every 3 months, 30% of teachers agreed, 25% strongly agreed, 27% disagreed and 18% strongly disagreed as depicted by the pie below. Almost 55% agree to have regular in-service trainings while 45% do not agree that teachers should have a regular in-service trainings.

Table 1 (Frequency of Training)

Question No. 1	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Teachers should get a regular training every three months	30%	25%	27%	18%

Figure 1.

Q2. What in-service training programs and opportunities for career development of teachers in the Government schools are provided?

During the interviews of School Managers, to the question should a regular in-service training be arranged for the teachers, 18% agreed, 11% strongly agreed, 27% disagreed and 44% strongly disagreed to it. A total of 29% is convinced that teachers should get a regular in-service trainings while 71% think that as not important. The chart and graph below depict the results.

Table.2 (In-service Trainings for Teachers)

Question No. 1	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Should In-Service training arranged for the teachers	18%	11%	27%	44%

Figure.2

Q3. What is relation of Teacher Training and the Career Development, how career development could take place by promoting teacher trainings?

To the question: Will the teachers’ performance improve after the trainings and the continuous Professional Development (CPD), 29% agreed, 42% strongly agreed, 15% disagreed and 14% disagreed strongly as shown below, a total of 71% are of the opinion that trainings would improve their performance but 29% were not convinced for that.

Table. 3 (Training and Performance)

Question No. 3	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Teacher’s performance will improve after training & CPD	29%	42%	15%	14%

Figure.3

FINDINGS

Based on the data, the following findings were revealed:

- 55% teachers thought that they need a training once a 3 months while 45% teachers thought they do not need it once in three months, some of them agreed that it should be once in a six month or once in a year. The results have been depicted in figure 1.10.1
- 29% school managers thought it was possible to arrange regular in-service trainings for teachers but 71% school managers did not agree, results are depicted in figure 1.10.2
- 45% teachers agreed that there should be academic trainings for the teachers while 55% thought that teachers should only get administrative trainings, the results have been depicted in figure 1.10.3

DISCUSSIONS

The above findings lead to certain conclusions and recommendations, these findings reveal that there is a lot of work to be done on the part of the policy makers and school managements. It is to train the school managers before reaching the teachers. The half sample appreciates the regularity of the training which is an encouraging sign and there may be an underlined reasons for the other half not doing that and finding those reasons and addressing them might help.

Mostly teachers of the government schools show a lot of resentment to attend any training after the school hours or the trainings which are not paid. There is basic lack of motivation to give importance to such trainings and that’s why at the moment either there are no trainings or a lot of resistance to going to training. Lack of exposure to such trainings has also affected the results.

The concept of different types of trainings and especially the academic trainings is also missing, teachers were hardly aware of any academic or pedagogical trainings and that could be a reason also that not many teachers thought that the academic trainings could also matter to career.

Similarly over half sample is convinced to have the academic trainings and the other half is not convinced for them, the reason may be the kind of trainings which have been offered so far. The nature of trainings may therefore, be scrutinized before reaching on the conclusions and recommendations. Similarly the matter of the

students and teachers performance improvement after the trainings is also connected to certain conditions and given the corrupt practices at board exams and the cheating culture, the result of the students may really not depend upon the ability of teacher other training.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the preceding findings, the following conclusions are set:

1. Almost 50% teachers realized that they are in need of academics trainings but there is no in-service training opportunity available for them.
2. Most of the teachers opted for the administrative trainings because so far they are hardly exposed to any academic trainings. It came to them rather a surprise that there could be academic trainings. There seems a clear negligence on the part of the authorities who have never arranged relevant trainings for them.
3. The willingness to get trained regularly was found 90% among the teachers of the adopted school as their mind-set has been trained accordingly. This is lacking in the other government teachers who are working in typical government environment.
4. It was also seen that many performing and active teachers also did not want to commit to training as they did not want to struggle and work hard. They were happy to have good time without any monitoring and answerability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The researcher recommends that the Department of Education and Literacy, Government of Sindh should take interest in developing teachers professionally by grooming them through regular trainings. These trainings could be of three monthly or six monthly. Continuous Professional Development is a vital part of any profession and the concerned authorities should make an elaborative program for that.
2. Most of the teachers have been sent for administrative and state trainings like census training, election training, polio campaign training etc. Teachers have hardly ever experienced that there could be any other trainings apart from these state interest driven trainings. A taste of academic trainings thus needs to be created.
3. The researcher recommends that teachers should be given equal incentives to go to the academic trainings where their content mastery and pedagogical skills are enhanced. So far teachers only get monetary incentives for such administrative trainings which motivated them to accept offers for such trainings.
4. After the trainings a mechanism of follow up should be set up without which no training could have a lasting impact on a profession. In the sample schools there are no trainings initiated by the government of the Department of Education and Literacy and if at all there are such trainings, there is no follow up of the trainings,
5. Teachers should also be interviewed in detail and their fears may be addressed. Most of them realize that they need certain trainings but fear their limitations and are scared to fail. The trainings should be provided according to their basic needs.
6. The Town Officers (TOs), Additional District Officers (ADOs), the District Officers (Dos) and the Deputy District Officers (DDOs) should all be trained about the importance of academic training for the teachers so that they keep it a high priority in their programs to train teachers. If they know the importance of content focused training and pedagogical trainings, they would guide the teachers accordingly and make the relevant policies.

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